

WEIGHT REDUCTION OF AUTOMOBILE USING ADVANCED POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITES

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Keywords: TPO, Nanocomposites, LFT

1 General Introduction

In recent years, the reduction of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions has become one of the most important issues in automotive industry. Therefore, the European Union intends to limit CO₂ emissions per vehicle up to 120g on average by 2012 [1-3]. Lighter weight components can contribute to lower overall automotive weight, resulting in reduced fuel consumption and less CO₂ emissions [4-6]. To achieve this goal, we have developed advanced polypropylene (PP) composites for automotive parts: 1) TPO composites with high melt flow rate for the thin wall bumper fascia 2) PP/Nanoclay composites for side sill moldings 3) Long glass fiber reinforced PP composites for door plate module and bumper back beam. We demonstrated that these materials were successfully applied to automotive parts.

2 Functional TPO composites

2.1 High flow TPO

Bumper system consists of three components such as bumper fascia, energy absorber and bumper back beam. The bumper fascia is a decorative covering that is placed over the bumper reinforcement. The weight reduction in the bumper fascia was extensively studied. Apart from the direct weight reduction by material substitution, reducing the thickness of parts shows an alternative possibility for lightweighting. However, thin-wall injection molding of bumper fascia presents several technical challenges. Due to the rapid cooling of the polymer melt, the material should flow easily. Thus, the material should have enough impact strength and high stiffness to retain mechanical properties of the final product. Honam Petrochemical Corporation (HPC) introduced high melt flow rate PP composites (SRX-373), which has excellent processability and physical properties. The difference of physical properties between conventional TPO composites and SRX-373 is shown in Table 1. In order to reduce

flow resistance, we increased the melt flow index of SRX-373 about 40-45 g/10min without any loss of mechanical properties.

Table 1. The difference of physical properties between conventional TPO composites and SRX-373

Properties	Unit	conventional TPO	SRX-373
MFI	g/10min	10-15	40-45
FM	kg/cm ²	10,000	20,000
IZOD	kgcm/cm	NB	NB

Generally, addition of talc to PP provides an increase in stiffness, but these particles are stress-concentrators and result in concomitant decrease in impact strength. To improve stiffness without loss of impact strength, SRX-373 was manufactured by special extrusion system and formulated with high impact strength polypropylene, rubber and talc.

Table 2. weight reduction of bumper fascia applied with SRX-373

Properties	conventional TPO	SRX-373
Wall thickness	3 mm	2.5 mm
Weight	4.1kg	3.2 kg

In 2009, SRX-373 was successfully applied to bumper fascia in a commercial model of Hyundai motors. Table 2. shows weight reduction of bumper fascia applied with SRX-373. Compared with conventional TPO, the wall thickness was reduced from 3mm to 2.5mm. Total weight reduction was about 1 kg/car. Thus, SRX-373 offered high level surface aesthetics and faster cycle time for the thin wall bumper fascia.

2.2 PP/Nanoclay composites

PP/Nanoclay composites were developed in order to decrease the weight of side sill molding which is placed under door exterior parts. Nanoclay is composed of platelets that are about 1 nm in

thickness and around 1,000 nm in lateral dimensions. The surface area of fully exfoliated nanoclay platelets is about 750m²/g. This is 5 to 10 times the surface area per gram achievable with ordinary mineral fillers. (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. The comparison of surface area between talc and nanoclay in the polymer matrix.

In this reason, exfoliated nanoclay in the PP shows excellent properties, such as high stiffness, high gas barrier property, with increasing flame retardancy. However, separation of the nanoclay platelets in the PP is very difficult because nanoclay platelets are strongly held together by ionic bonding. In order to disperse the nanoclay in the PP matrix, PP-g-MAH was used as a compatibilizer. PP-g-MAH with high MAH contents was effective to disperse large surface area of nanoclay in PP matrix.

Fig. 2. XRD spectrum of nanoclay and PP/nanoclay composite.

XRD spectra of Nanoclay and PP/nanoclay hybrid were measured to calculate d-spacing of nanoclay interlayer. In Fig. 2. natural organo-nanoclay shows a (001) diffraction peak at 2theta=2.65, which corresponds to an interlayer spacing of 3.3 nm. However, the intercalated nanoclay in PP/nanoclay composite revealed no (001) typical peak in XRD spectra. According to interlayer spacing in TEM image, the (001) peak can be shown approximately

at 2theta=1.5, but the characteristic peak at small angle can not be detected in wide angle X-ray spectrum. Moreover, the second and the third peaks also disappeared. At least, it could be assumed that the interlayer spacing of nanoclay was expanded up to above 5 nm. Highly-dispersed nanoclay in PP matrix was shown in SEM and TEM images (Fig. 3). The nanoclay bundle size could be reduced into 50~100 nm with these strategies.

Fig. 3. SEM images of PP/Nanoclay composites: a) X500, b) X2,000, and TEM images: c) X20,000, d) X200,000.

Fig. 4. shows photograph and physical property of side sill molding applied with PP/nanoclay hybrid (nanoclay: 7 wt%). The fabricated PP/nanoclay/Rubber composites were being applied into automotive parts: side sill molding, roof rack cover, and engine cover, etc. Typically, the side sill molding was chosen as the first application part by automobile manufacturer. Talc and rubber contents were 40 wt% and 25 wt% and the shrinkage was 0.4. However, PP/nanoclay/rubber composites displayed 0.4% of shrinkage only using 10 wt% organo-nanoclay (inorganic contents: just 6 wt%) and 20 wt% of rubber. Compared with 1.2 g/cm³ of Talc-PP composite density, the density of PP/nanoclay composite was just 0.95 g/cm³, in other words, the part's weight could be reduced by 21 percent. The sum of weight reduction was about 1 kg per a car. This result was very meaningful in automobile company. In addition, the physical property of PP/nanoclay composites was higher than the standard of different automobile manufacturer.

Properties	conventional TPO	PP/nanoclay composite.
Filler	Talc 40%	Nanoclay 10%
Weight	4.8 kg (2.4 kg/ea)	3.6 kg (1.8kg/ea)

Fig. 4. Photograph and physical property of side sill molding applied with PP/nanoclay composite (nanoclay: 7 wt%, rubber: 20 wt%).

PP/Nanoclay composites revealed 21% of weight reduction instead of conventional PP/Talc composites. Total weight reduction of car was calculated with above 1kg. Automotive manufacturer is willing to expand the application of PP/Nanoclay composites to various automotive parts such as roof rack cover, cowl top cover, engine cover, and so on.

3 Long glass fiber reinforced PP composites

3.1 Weight reduction of door plate module

Traditionally the structural parts in automotive are made of steel because of its performance and safety of the car. To reduce weight of these parts, SAMBARK LFT (subsidiary company of HPC) have developed long glass fiber reinforced PP composites (PP/LFT).

Fig. 5. Impregnation system of SUPRAN® LFT.

Compared with metal, PP/LFT has several characteristics such as light weight, corrosion resistance and design flexibility for complex geometries. SUPRAN®, the trade name of the injection moldable PP/LFT, is produced by unique

impregnation technology with SAMBARK LFT's own patent (Fig. 5). Using a unique impregnation system, each glass fiber is fully wetted with polypropylene during the manufacturing process. In this reason, SUPRAN® has much better mechanical properties than conventional short fiber reinforced thermoplastics (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. The comparison of mechanical properties between short fiber reinforced thermoplastics and SUPRAN® LFT

In 2009, SUPRAN® LFT was firstly employed to door plate module in YF sonata (Hyundai motors). A door plate module made of SUPRAN (Fig. 7) showed 20% part consolidation and 30% weight reduction (4kg per car).

Fig. 7. A door plate module made of PP/LFT composites

3.2 Weight reduction of bumper back beam

The bumper back beam is the main structure to absorb the collision energy. Bumper back beam is usually made of steel or aluminum materials. In order to reduce the weight of automotive and enhance the energy absorption capacity, SAMBARK has developed woven long fiber hybrid thermoplastic composites (WLFT). WLFT is new material of sheet that is hybridized with fully impregnated WFT (woven fiber glass thermoplastic mat) and LFT. And also new bumper back beam processing technology, so called Win-LFT, was developed. Win-LFT is processed by combining compression process with injection molding. A method of manufacturing Win-LFT consists of two steps: a) Inserting WLFT sheets into the mold. b)

LFT Injection molding with high compression pressure (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. The manufacturing process of Win-LFT.

In 2010, Win-LFT bumper back beam was commercialized to famous model of Hyundai motors. It was successfully designed with less weight compared to steel bumper back beam. A bumper back beam made of Win-LFT showed 35% weight reduction (about 2.2kg per car)

4 Summary

One of the alternative methods to reduce energy consumption is weight reduction of automotive parts. To achieve this goal, we have developed advanced polypropylene (PP) composites for automotive parts: 1) TPO composites with high melt flow rate 2) PP/Nanoclay composites 3) Long glass fiber reinforced PP composites. We demonstrated that these materials were successfully applied to automotive parts: bumper fascia, side sill molding, door plate module and bumper back beam. In the result, they led to the total weight reduction of about 8 kg per car. Moreover, the requirements of these lightweight materials will be increased more and more in the automotive industry.

References

- [1] H. Adam “Carbon fiber in automotive applications”, *Materials & Design*, Vol. 18, No 349, 1997.
- [2] A.C. Karmaker, J.A. Youngquist. “; Injection molding of polypropylene reinforced with short jute fibers”, *Applied Polymer Science*, Vol. 62, No 1142, 1996.
- [3] Manson J-AE, Wakeman MD, Bemet N., “Composite processing and manufacturing” , *Comprehensive Composite Materials*, Vol. 2, pp. 577–607, 2000.
- [4] Brylawski MM, Lovins AB. “Advanced composites” the car is at the crossroads Proceedings of 43rd international society for the advancement of materials and process engineering (SAMPE) symposium and exhibition, 1998.
- [5] Ping Z, Yu Z, Guanlong C, Zhongqin L. “Research on lightweight of auto-body material based on

crashworthiness simulation”, *Chin J Mech Eng*, Vol 9, No. 41, 2005

- [6] Zhang Y, Zhu P, Chen GL, Lin ZQ. “Study on structural lightweight design of automotive front side rail based on response surface method”. *ASME J Mech Des*, 2007.